

Ethical Practices in Business: Pathways to Sustainable Growth

By

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Abstract: *Every business aspires to achieve continuous growth throughout its existence. This aspiration for growth extends beyond the business itself to include its various stakeholders, such as shareholders, employees, customers, and society at large. Businesses rely on inputs from society and convert them into outputs to ensure their long-term survival. However, it is the pursuit of sustainable growth and development that truly enables a business to navigate the various stages of its life cycle, effectively face challenges, and capitalize on opportunities presented by both the external and internal environments. Sustainable growth and development are vital for maintaining the health and vitality of a business over the long term. Unlike mere growth, which can be short-lived and potentially detrimental if not managed properly, sustainable growth emphasizes a balanced approach that considers economic, social, and environmental factors. This holistic perspective ensures that a business can thrive not only in the present but also in the future, creating value for all its stakeholders. This paper aims to explore why sustainable growth is preferred over mere growth, delving into the different aspects of corporate governance that support this objective. By examining key pillars of corporate governance, such as accountability, transparency, and stakeholder engagement, we can better understand how these practices contribute to the long-term success and resilience of businesses. Ultimately, this study seeks to highlight the importance of integrating corporate ethical practices into the core strategies of businesses to achieve sustainable growth and development.*

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Ethical Practices, Sustainable Growth, Stakeholder Management, Corporate Social Responsibility

Introduction: Growth is a fundamental aspiration for every business, driven by the desire to continuously evolve and thrive throughout its existence. This quest for growth is not confined to the business as an economic entity alone; it extends to the various stakeholders associated with the business, including shareholders, employees, customers, and society at large (Freeman et al., 2007). Businesses extract inputs from society and convert them into outputs, thereby ensuring their long-term survival and generating wealth in the form of profits and values. These resources are crucial for meeting current demands and preserving the business's health to address future needs. Thus, the concept of growth must transcend mere expansion and encompass sustainable growth and development.

Sustainable growth is vital for businesses to remain resilient and robust during the various stages of their life cycles. It ensures that businesses are equipped to face challenges and seize opportunities provided by both external and internal environments, allowing for progressive development (Elkington, 1997). Unlike short-term growth, which can be fleeting and potentially harmful if not managed appropriately, sustainable growth integrates economic, social, and environmental considerations. This balanced approach ensures the business's longevity and its ability to create lasting value for all stakeholders.

The concept of sustainable development, as defined by the World Commission on Environment and Development in 1987, emphasizes meeting present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own. It highlights two key concepts: the essential needs of the world's poor, to which overriding priority should be given, and the limitations imposed by technology and social organization on the environment's capacity to meet present and future needs. This ethical framework underscores the importance of integrating sustainability into business practices.

Corporate governance plays a crucial role in achieving sustainable growth and development. Effective corporate governance establishes a framework that enables businesses to achieve their objectives, manage risks, and ensure accountability. It involves the relationships between a company's management, its board, shareholders, and other stakeholders. Good governance

practices foster trust, transparency, and ethical behaviour, which are essential for long-term success.

Objectives of this study

This study aims to explore why sustainable growth is preferred over mere growth by delving into the various aspects of corporate governance that support this objective. The following objectives have been set for this study:

1. To analyse the main objectives and key pillars of corporate governance.
2. To examine the role of corporate governance in promoting sustainable growth and development.
3. To identify and assess the different challenges faced in corporate governance.
4. To evaluate the key pillars of corporate governance.

By examining these aspects, we seek to understand how corporate governance practices can contribute to the long-term success and resilience of businesses, highlighting the importance of integrating ethical practices into core business strategies to achieve sustainable growth and development.

Research Methodology: Research is an organized and systematic way of finding or exploring research questions. The present study is an attempt to analyze corporate governance and its role in sustainable growth and development. In the present study secondary sources have been used i.e. books, journals, newspapers and websites.

Corporate Ethical Practices Vs Sustainable Growth and Development: why the sustainable growth is preferred over just growth? The reasons for this is not only one but many. Some reasons are legislative and other necessity and some are voluntary which are as follows-

- Government has legally imposed several rules and regulations over corporates for achieving the objective of sustainable growth and development for social welfare and responsibility in the form of corporate social responsibility and corporate governance.

- Business has to repay to its stakeholders for their resources which includes its customers, society, employees, shareholders etc.
- For its own survival for the longer period as no business is established just for one day, they all aspire to stay here for longer and longest.
- Sustainability is the tool in the hands of business which keeps it floating during the various stages of economic and business life cycle be it the phase of boom, recession, depression and recovery.
- Sustainable growth is the one which helps the business in maintaining its present health and at the same time develop a support system for it to preserve its health and develop its wealth for itself and its future prospects in the future also.
- It provides the corporate an edge over the others in meeting needs of competition be it by developing its goodwill, increasing its customers, fulfilling its social responsibility by preserving environment etc. or any other way.

The value of sustainability has been analyzed by corporates from every direction—revenues, profits, and share prices—and it is clear that, in some circumstances, sustainability can pay off. However, sustainability is more than just about firm-level benefits. Businesses, business schools, and society recognize that the current course of production and consumption cannot be sustained within our natural resource limits. Businesses develop the products and services consumed by individuals around the world. However, a high degree of priority has been placed on the interests of shareholders, who place their trust in corporations to use their investment funds wisely and effectively is common to all good corporate governance regimes. Also, irrespective of the model, there are three different forms of corporate responsibilities which all models do respect:

Political Responsibilities: the basic political obligations are abiding by legitimate law; respect for the system of rights and the principles of constitutional state.

Social Responsibilities: the corporate ethical responsibilities, which the company understands and promotes either as a community with shared values or as a part of larger community with shared values (Garriga et al., 2004).

Economic Responsibilities: acting in accordance with the logic of competitive markets to earn profits on the basis of innovation and respect for the rights/democracy of the shareholders which can be expressed in terms of managements' obligation as 'maximizing shareholders value'.

In addition, business ethics and corporate awareness of the environmental and societal interest of the communities, within which they operate, can have an impact on the reputation and long-term performance of corporations (Dyllick et al., 2002).

Role of Corporate Ethics in Sustainable Growth & Development:

The essence of good corporate governance is ensuring trustworthy relations between the corporation and its stakeholders. Therefore, good governance involves a lot more than compliance. Good corporate governance is a culture and a climate of **C**onsistency, **R**esponsibility, **A**ccountability, **F**airness, **T**ransparency, and **E**ffectiveness that is **D**eployed throughout the organization (the 'CRAFTED' principles of governance) (Garriga et al., 2004).

Boards have the basic responsibility to ensure sustainable improvements in corporate valuations by providing strategic guidance and oversight regarding management decisions, as well as selecting and changing the management whenever necessary. Governance presupposes the consideration of two fundamental conditions, i.e., that:

- only competitive companies, that are able to respond adequately to market needs and create value, can make a long-term contribution to sustainable growth; and
- the ability to obtain broad approval and qualitative-quantitative resources suitable for sustaining company growth and internal productivity depends on effective interaction with all classes of stakeholders, with long-term consequences for financial result optimization and company value.

Success can only be achieved on a sustainable basis, if boards behave as a role model for implementing the CRAFTED principles of governance in their own operations and ensure that the corporation follows these principles in making key decisions.

The board of directors is the most important element in corporate structures. The tone at the top determines the tune in the middle. Clear separation of management rights (taking initiative and implementation) and governance rights (guidance, approval, and oversight), is critical in minimizing potential ‘agency’ risks of the management such as:

- Fraud
- lethargy, focusing on excuses as opposed to results
- being too risk averse that may lead to overinvestment
- being too risk prone

Issues such as the composition of boards, their agenda and processes for decision-making, and how they Learn to continuously improve the governance of the corporation, critically influence the both the quality of decisions and of management. The main responsibilities of the board is to provide effective Oversight and strategic Guidance for the management. The quality of their decisions is critically dependent on the quality of the Information they have. Establishing a Culture that sets the right tone at the top is critical for establishing the ‘trust’ for the corporation with all its stakeholders (The ‘LOGIC’ of governance).

The success of the board depends on making sound judgments in numerous situations that involve balancing different interests:

- risk versus reward;
- short term versus long term;
- effective oversight versus motivating management;
- ethical considerations versus market practices; and
- competing interests of different stakeholders.

Good corporate governance is very important for sustainable development, not only for the individual company, but also for the economy as a whole. Therefore, the quality of governance should be continuously improved and good governance should be promoted. However, what is not measured cannot be improved. Hence, there is a need for a model to measure the quality of corporate governance (Eccles et al., 2012).

Key Pillars of Corporate Ethical Practices:

The three key pillars of corporate governance are the Board of Directors, the Shareholders and the Management. The pivotal role in any system of corporate governance is performed by the board of directors. It is accountable to the stakeholders and directs and controls the management. It stewards the company, sets its strategic aim and financial goals and oversees their implementation, puts in place adequate internal controls and periodically reports the activities and progress of the company in the company in a transparent manner to all the stakeholders. The shareholders' role in corporate governance is to appoint the directors and the auditors and to hold the board accountable for the proper governance of the company by requiring the board to provide them periodically with the requisite information in a transparent fashion, of the activities and progress of the company. The responsibility of the management is to undertake the management of the company in terms of the direction provided by the board, to put in place adequate control systems and to ensure their operation and to provide information to the board on a timely basis and in a transparent manner to enable the board to monitor the accountability of management to it.

The underlying principles of corporate governance revolve around three basic inter-related segments. These are: **Integrity and Fairness Transparency and Disclosures Accountability and Responsibility**. The application of proper governance principles demands a clear focus on sustainable growth as the basis for risk minimization in order to ensure long-term company success. In other words, a company's effectiveness implies the assumption of a global responsibility concept based on strict compliance with the law, the creation of constructive relationships with all of society and respect for the environment. Of course, this does not mean losing sight of the importance of creating value and adequately compensating risk capital providers. Instead, it means emphasizing the interdependence of corporate image, results (whether financial or otherwise), operating transparency and the obtaining of broad approval and resources (Carroll et al., 2010).

Constituents/ Challenges of Good Corporate Ethical Practices:

The Main Constituents of Good Corporate Governance are:

Role and powers of Board: the foremost requirement of good corporate governance is the clear identification of powers, roles, responsibilities and accountability of the Board, CEO and the Chairman of the board.

Legislation: a clear and unambiguous legislative and regulatory framework is fundamental to effective corporate governance.

Code of Conduct: it is essential that an organization's explicitly prescribed codes of conduct are communicated to all stakeholders and are clearly understood by them. There should be some system in place to periodically measure and evaluate the adherence to such code of conduct by each member of the organization.

Board Independence: An independent board is essential for sound corporate governance. It means that the board is capable of assessing the performance of managers with an objective perspective. Hence, the majority of board members should be independent of both the management team and any commercial dealings with the company. Such independence ensures the effectiveness of the board in supervising the activities of management as well as make sure that there are no actual or perceived conflicts of interests.

Board Skills: In order to be able to undertake its functions effectively, the board must possess the necessary blend of qualities, skills, knowledge and experience so as to make quality contribution. It includes operational or technical expertise, financial skills, legal skills as well as knowledge of government and regulatory requirements.

Management Environment: includes setting up of clear objectives and appropriate ethical framework, establishing due processes, providing for transparency and clear enunciation of responsibility and accountability, implementing sound business planning, encouraging business risk assessment, having right people and right skill for jobs, establishing clear boundaries for

acceptable behaviour, establishing performance evaluation measures and evaluating performance and sufficiently recognizing individual and group contribution.

Board Appointments: To ensure that the most competent people are appointed in the board, the board positions must be filled through the process of extensive search. A well-defined and open procedure must be in place for reappointments as well as for appointment of new directors.

Board Induction and Training: is essential to ensure that directors remain abreast of all development, which are or may impact corporate governance and other related issues.

Board Meetings: are the forums for board decision making. These meetings enable directors to discharge their responsibilities. The effectiveness of board meetings is dependent on carefully planned agendas and providing relevant papers and materials to directors sufficiently prior to board meetings.

Strategy Setting: The objective of the company must be clearly documented in a long term corporate strategy including an annual business plan together with achievable and measurable performance targets and milestones.

Business and Community Obligations: though the basic activity of a business entity is inherently commercial yet it must also take care of community's obligations. The stakeholders must be informed about the approval by the proposed and ongoing initiatives taken to meet the community obligations.

Financial and Operational Reporting: the board requires comprehensive, regular, reliable, timely, correct and relevant information in a form and of a quality that is appropriate to discharge its function of monitoring corporate performance.

Monitoring the Board Performance: The board must monitor and evaluate its combined performance and also monitor individual director's performance at periodic intervals, using key performance indicators besides peer review.

Audit Committee: is inter alia responsible for liaison with management, internal and statutory auditors, reviewing the adequacy of internal control and compliance with significant policies and procedures, reporting to the board on the key issues.

Risk Management: risk is an important element of corporate functioning and governance. There should be a clearly established process of identifying, analyzing and treating risks, which could prevent the company from effectively achieving its objectives.

Challenges:

Companies pool capital from a large investor base both in domestic and in the international capital markets. In this context, Investment is ultimately an act of faith in the ability of a company's management and the ability of a company's management is fully dependent if there are the good practices which are being followed by it. Therefore, the need is to strengthen the corporate governance so that the following may be achieved.

1. To promote or to increase awareness among entrepreneurs' adoption of good corporate governance practices, which are the integral element for doing and managing business.
2. To ensure the quality of audit that is at the root of effective corporate governance by making the Auditor accountable for the disclosure of financial information.
3. To make the Board of Directors as well as the CEOs and CFOs accountable for the discharge of their duties with the proper use of their rights within the powers.
4. To form an appropriate system to check the Directors independence in the board and to monitor the work of Audit firms.
5. To pay special attention in the quality and effectiveness of the legal, administrative and regulatory framework.
6. To increase the shareholder activism i.e. the exercise and enforcement of rights by minority shareholders with the objective of enhancing shareholder value over the long term.
7. To infuse India's Business Culture with a "Spirit of Corporate Governance" to maintain sustainable and effective corporate governance.

8. To implement more robust Bankruptcy Laws which are a key component of any corporate governance system?
9. To resolve the conflict between the dominant shareholders and the minority shareholders by improving the rights of minority shareholders.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the support for good corporate governance practices is essential for businesses to achieve a multitude of benefits. These include reducing costs through eco-efficiencies, particularly in energy use, mitigating environmental and social risks, building a strong reputation and competitive advantage, complying with regulations, satisfying investor expectations, and supporting advocacy efforts. Regardless of their motivations, investors and consumers seek reliable information about the companies they engage with. Sustainable businesses demonstrate resilience by creating economic value, fostering healthy ecosystems, and building strong communities. These businesses are better equipped to withstand external shocks due to their integration with healthy economic, social, and environmental systems. Consequently, the benefits of good corporate governance and sustainability practices include reduced corruption, increased transparency, enhanced convenience, revenue growth, and cost reductions.

Overall, embedding corporate governance and ethical practices into the core strategies of businesses is crucial for achieving sustainable growth and long-term success.

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